

Recommended citation: Steger, F., Brade, K., Schweiger, H., Nitsche, A., & Belski, I. (2017). Teaching Energy Storages by Means of a Student Battery Cell Test System . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 169-176). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698017.

Teaching Energy Storages by means of a Student Battery Cell Test System

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ABSTRACT

Energy storage systems are vital for success of electric mobility. Thus, knowledge of energy storage systems behaviours is essential for the development of electric vehicles. Universities and vocational training institutions are urgently required to educate specialists in electrical storage systems. A safe and easy-manageable battery test system was developed to improve the outcomes of student learning of battery storage systems and to allow practice for future employment through hands-on laboratory training. This test system supports temperature-dependent experiments with different cell types including lithium-ion cells, and incorporates a redundant safety shut-off module that protects students from being injured. Based on this system, a new energy storage laboratory course was developed. This course covers four main content areas of battery energy storage: (1) contact & isolation resistance, (2) open-circuit voltage, (3) internal resistance & power, and (4) energy of cells. This new laboratory course was introduced in summer 2016 and has already been conducted with several full-time and part-time student groups.

Conference Key Areas: Open and Online Engineering Education, Engineering Education Research, Sustainability and Engineering Education

Keywords: Student Experiments, Energy Storage Systems, Battery Test System

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INTRODUCTION

Transportation currently experiences a major period of change that is focused on minimizing the environmental impact associated with motor vehicles. Battery-powered electric vehicles play an important role in development of greener cars that minimize pollution in big cities. One of the central challenges for the design of these vehicles is the efficient storage and provision of power and energy by an energy storage system on board. As such, academic qualification in this area is essential for the mid- to long-term success of electric mobility [1]. Highly trained professionals are needed and universities as well as vocational training institutions have to find ways to meet this industry demand [2]. Thus, teaching modules on electrical energy storage systems are increasingly incorporated into existing and new study programs related to electric mobility. It has been reported that when practical training complements theoretical lectures, it significantly improves the outcomes of student learning [3]. In addition, laboratories provide valuable hands-on practice for future employment [4].

1 BATTERY TRAINING

The Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt (THI) offers a wide range of qualification programs in the field of electric mobility. Students may choose between various full-time and part-time bachelor and master degree programs, which include lectures on electrochemical energy storage systems. With a profile of a University of Applied Sciences, the consolidation of theoretical knowledge by means of practical experiments in the teaching laboratory is of particular importance for all of these study programs [5].

To prepare graduates for fieldwork with electrochemical cells, a new energy storage laboratory has been developed, which must meet conflicting framework conditions. On the one hand, laboratory space, financial resources, and the students' time are limited while on the other hand, science about electrochemical cells is a growing and rapidly evolving field, which gets increasingly complex to teach. Therefore it was decided to reduce the new laboratory to the most relevant knowledge of battery systems. Students should strengthen their basic understanding of electrochemical storage systems and learn about the practical behaviour of battery cells – building up universal knowledge for their future career. The focus was laid on practical knowledge of the most important parameters of battery cells. Students should be able to determine these parameters self-sufficiently by means of appropriate experimental setups – competencies that are necessary to design energy storage systems.

The identified learning objectives were grouped into four main content areas: (1) contact & isolation resistance, (2) open-circuit voltage, (3) internal resistance & power, and (4) energy & efficiency.

These content areas are taught during five discrete laboratory sessions, three hours in duration each. These laboratory sessions lead to a workshop in which the individual students' measurements are used to parameterize a simulation model and to design an energy storage system in Matlab/Simulink.

The initial plan to conduct a set of laboratory experiments on battery storage led to the specifications of the battery test system for such laboratories. Unfortunately, no fitting equipment, which would allow execution of the planned experiments within the abovementioned framework conditions could be found on the market. Ready-to-use industrial battery cell test benches and temperature cabinets are generally large, multichannel, and expensive devices, which are impractical for laboratory work in small learning groups. Thus, a small and flexible cell test system was developed, which

allows safe and effective individual learning experiences for the students. The development was funded by the German Federal Government's Showcase Program "Academic Education Initiative on Electromobility". The developed benchtop test system supports temperature-dependent experiments with lithium-ion cells and other types of energy storage cells, while a safety shut-off module ensures a high degree of safety during operation at all times. The combination of all functions required for an energy storage laboratory in a compact design is a unique feature of this test system.

Funding by the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science allowed a complete teaching laboratory at THI to be equipped with 13 battery test systems. The hardware and the newly created laboratory experiments were tested in various study programs on electric mobility [6]. The students have evaluated practical experiments that utilized the new system more favourably than similar experiments conducted using computer simulations [7].

2 BATTERY TEST SYSTEM

The battery test system is based on a 19-inch table top case of three rack unit height. Its housing consists of three modules with standardized plug-in technology according to IEC 60297-3-101, and allows simple adaptation of the test system to the desired functional range or future developments through connectors according to IEC 60603-2.

The functions of the three modules that are shown in *Fig. 1* and *Fig. 2* cover all needs of the energy storage laboratory. Included are a potentiostat/galvanostat module for cell measuring operations, a thermostat module, and a safety module.

Fig. 1. Battery test system for hands-on laboratories. Students strengthen their basic understanding of electrochemical storage and learn about the behaviour of cells.

As even the production of the tester was used to educate students, the circuit boards were designed by the researcher in a way to enable easy manual assembly by student assistants in a separate project. Thus, most components are in the relatively large SMD format 0805. An ARM Cortex M4 processor was used as an arithmetic unit in all modules. The housing including all submodules and integrated power supply unit weighs 11.5 kg.

Fig. 2. Battery Test System, from left to right: thermostat, potentiostat/galvanostat, safety switch off module

2.1 Potentiostat/Galvanostat

The central element of the tester is a potentiostat/galvanostat. It allows to conduct experiments with small single cells with amp-hour capacity up to 600 mAh. Currents and voltages can be applied to the cell and may be measured time discrete. The voltage range is symmetrical for measurements up to ± 12 V, with currents up to 8 A for discharging and 4 A for charging. In addition to the DC component, an AC voltage of lower amplitude can be overlaid for impedance measurements. In this case, the device determines the impedance's magnitude for frequencies up to 10 kHz and its phase for frequencies up to 5 kHz. The new test system offers a continuous frequency range with 1 Hz resolution.

Apart from technical implementation, finding a good compromise between cost/production efforts and measuring accuracy was challenging. A test system should be easy to build and to maintain, and at the same time should be accurate enough to provide a realistic test environment for the students. Therefore, focus was laid on optimized measuring accuracy and not on the exact analogous injection of current and voltage. If the system injects inaccurately, the resulting errors will automatically be corrected by the measured data (*Fig. 3*). For voltage measurements the error is below 10 mV, for current measurements the error stays below 5 mA in the specified temperature range ($21\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). The down sampled data rate for the time discrete transfer to the computer is adjusted automatically in the range between 312 Hz and 625 Hz.

The galvanostat/potentiostat is controlled from a laboratory computer via serial communication (USB) using C# and Java-based control programs as well as a LabVIEW driver. The Java program was used for the student laboratory, because it is similar to software used for industrial test equipment regarding architecture and user interface. The program was developed during a master's thesis and allows learners to freely program the steps and control structures to implement a certain experiment. Conformity to industrial test benches prepares the students for their later professional life.

Fig. 3. Simplified working principle of the galvanostat. Actual current and voltage are converted to digital values using two synchronized ADCs. After downsampling the values are submitted to the controlling computer. The current is compared with the target current by software and controls the DAC.

2.2 Thermostat

A major challenge for electric mobility is the strong temperature dependence of parameters of electrochemical energy storage systems [8]. Thus, it is important that students can comprehend the effects of high and low temperatures on the performance of battery cells. Unfortunately, this cannot be achieved using industrial temperature cabinets, which are optimized for testing larger test objects. These cabinets are too big in size, expensive and don't allow changing temperature of small single cells quickly enough to conduct a laboratory within two to three hours.

Besides the requirements on the equipment, the waiting time for a homogenous temperature distribution within the cells must be considered for the lesson preparation. To be able to carry out various temperature-dependent measurements during a lesson, especially the cooling performance is essential. For example, to conduct several tests on the internal resistance of a cell according to ISO 12405-1 within a teaching unit of three hours, cooling from room temperature to -18 °C was required within 20 minutes.

To avoid the disadvantages of convection cooling or fluid thermostats and to solve the problem of minimal time, a small, cost-effective, and rapidly responding two-stage thermoelectric cooler as shown in *Fig. 4* was integrated into the battery test system. Cooling and heating are based on Peltier elements, which allow temperature control in a range from -25 °C to 50 °C. To achieve rapid cooling (*Fig. 5*), the test cell is in direct contact with the metal on four sides. The chamber is made for cells with maximum dimensions 90 mm x 34 mm x 30 mm. The cooling stages are driven by two modulated H-Bridges, providing up to 250 W of power. Heat flux losses are reduced by a foam cube, which isolates the cooling device from the environment. The chamber temperature is measured with an absolute error below 1 K. This external cooling system weighs 5.0 kg, its dimensions (26 cm x 26 cm x 20 cm) allow for easy storage while not in use.

The thermostat supports remote control, utilizing the galvanostat/potentiostat module as mediator between the USB-communication and the CAN-based bus between all the modules.

Fig. 4. External heating and cooling system

Fig. 5. Max. cooling performance of three exemplary external heating/cooling systems, $T_{env}=25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

2.3 Safety switch off module

Lithium-ion battery cells are potentially dangerous. In case of mistreatment, they may burst or burn [8]. To ensure the safety of the students at all times, experiments must be either greatly simplified or prepared in step-by-step instructions, which the student has to follow without any degree of freedom. However, this style of instructions would preclude students from gaining skills of planning their experimental work, the skill that is at the core of the engineering profession.

To enable students gaining skills in planning experimental work, a special safety shut-off module is integrated into the test system. This shut-off module is pre-parameterized by the instructor and allows the students full autonomy in controlling the battery system, and minimizes the need for supervision. The module monitors three parameters of the test specimen: (i) current ($\pm 12\text{ A}$), (ii) voltage ($\pm 12\text{ V}$), and (iii) temperature. If the ranges of these parameters fell outside of the range permitted by the instructor, the module automatically disconnects the cell from the test system. It is important to note that the switch-off value may be configured to be pulse-length dependent, as most battery cells allow pulses outside the cell's specified range for a short time. Since this

safety shut-off module can neither be influenced intentionally nor unintentionally by a student, he has full freedom to program the potentiostat/galvanostat and may gain valuable learning experience through trial and error.

3 EXPERIMENTS

The developed test instructions are not given in a step by step style. Through decision-making freedom, instructions encourage reflection on the new topic in an environment that stimulates hands-on learning from experimental errors.

The following student experiments have been tested and improved iteratively since summer 2016: (1) Charging/discharging of different individual accumulator cells to measure the cell voltage as a function of the state of charge, (2) Determination of the internal resistance according to ISO 12405-1, (3) Determination of maximum achievable power dependent upon temperature, (4) Capacity determination dependent upon the load profile, (5) Measurements under a load profile in order to parametrize a Matlab/Simulink model, (6) Determination of energy efficiency under various conditions. All laboratory instructions were written to encourage learning through trial and error. They were specifically tailored to support theoretical knowledge acquired from the accompanying theory-based lecture. The biggest challenge while creating the experiments was the limited time for a single student's laboratory (e.g. to cool a specimen down, discharge, charge a cell, and to wait for stable states is extremely time consuming). It was often necessary to divide the students into subgroups, who obtained differently parametrized experiments (e.g. discharge rate) and to let them consider the collected data from all groups for evaluation. The laboratory was piloted in summer 2016 and repeated with improvements in 2017.

The aforementioned experiments are a selection for the study programs at THI. Ideas for additional experiments using the battery test system are: (1) Observing the behavior of cells under load in driving cycles, (2) Development of SoC/SoH determination methods, (3) Impedance spectroscopy, (4) Use of two lithium cells in series connection to demonstrate experiments using battery management systems.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The described battery test system allows students to easily conduct hands-on experiments in an energy storage laboratory. The students can carry out practical experiments on accumulator cells in a safe, flexible learning environment. Current focus lays on repeated evaluations of the practical training with different groups and types of students for stepwise improvements. The newly developed laboratory sessions and devices may give other educators a good starting point for battery laboratories. In addition to practical training at universities, the developed practical experiments and equipment can be used at other educational institutions as well as by training departments of industrial corporations. More than sixty percent of young people in Germany take part in the dual system of vocational training [9]. Practice-orientated vocational schools, technical colleges, or colleges for master craftspeople may use the hardware in combination with adjusted teaching material.

5 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors wish to thank the laboratory engineer Sönke Barra for his assistance while planning, preparing, and conducting the experiments. Also to Christoph Nebl and the student workers who helped to produce the devices. The Federal Ministry of Education and Research provided funding for the project "Academic Education Initiative for E-

Mobility Bavaria – Saxony" which was used for the development of the prototypes of the devices. The devices used in the laboratory were built from finance of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science at THI.

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